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“Ecosystem Services Assessment in the six NewLife4Drylands case study areas”

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Executive summary

The present document reports the ecosystem services assessment in the 6 NL4DL case study areas. The document describes the methodology applied for estimating the potential ecosystem services provision in the six NL4DL case study areas. The choice of how to estimate and map ecosystem service indicators depends on several factors, among which the overall purpose of the ecosystem service assessment, the data availability, the type of measurement needed to quantify the indicators, and the availability of human and financial resources. The purpose of the assessment is to integrate ground data and existing thematic data layers with remote sensing observations to account for temporal variations in ecosystem services supply with reference to a baseline. The proposed approach is tailored to tackle situations with limited or no availability of measured ground data and relies on the use of existing GIS data from freely accessible web resources and remote sensing indices (RSI) retrieved via Google Earth Engine. The indicators of ecosystem services provision and degradation process estimated and mapped in each case study area have been selected in agreement with project partners. The proposed methodology has allowed to assess and map the values of the selected ES indicator along with their relative changes with respect to the baseline years. Integrating of time dependent predictors from remote sensing in a spatially explicit digital mapping workflow has allowed to visualize where the changes occur and their relative magnitudes. The methodology proved to be sensitive enough to depict negative changes in ES supply stemming from land degradation processes due to different drivers acting at different scales, such as wildfires and drought, but also positive changes due to ecosystem recovery. The results presented in the report detect yearly changes, but the approach can be easily tailored to finer temporal scales.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	6
2. Ecosystem services assessment and mapping: the NL4DL approach and workflow	7
3. Spanish case study areas: El Bruc and El Nublo-Tamadaba	12
4. Greek case study areas: Asterousia and Nestos River delta	28
5. Italian case study areas: Alta Murgia and Palo Laziale	50
6. Conclusions	63
7. References.....	68

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AGCS	Above Ground carbon Stock (Standardised Indicator)
AGB	Above Ground Biomass (Standardised Indicator)
BI	Bare Index
CDHW	Compound Drought and Heatwaves event
CSA	Case Study Area
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DIED	Drought Induced Ecosystem Degradation (Standardised Indicator)
DP	Degradation Process
EC	Electrical conductivity
ES	Ecosystem Service
GEE	Google Earth Engine
IR	Infra-Red
LULC	Land Use / Land Cover
MLR	Multiple Linear Regression
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging spectroradiometer
NbS	Nature-based Solutions
NDBSI	Normalised Difference Bare Soil Index
NDSI	Normalised Difference Soil Index
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index

NDWI	Normalised Difference Water Index
NIR	Near Infra-Red
NPP	Net Primary Production
NL4DL	New Life for Drylands
RS	Remote Sensing
RSI	Remote Sensing Index/Indices
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation
SAC	Special Area for Conservation
SEC	Soil Erosion Control (Standardised Indicator)
SASI	Soil Adjusted Salinity Index
SCI	Site of Community Importance
SoSa	Soil Salinity
SoSI	Soil Salinity Index
SoSr	Soil Salinity risk (Standardised Indicator)
SPA	Special Protection Area
SWIR	Short Wave Infra-Red
TWI	Topographic Wetness Index

NewLife4Drylands
LIFE20 PRE/IT/000007

Deliverable A4.3 "Report on ecosystem services assessment in the NL4DL case study areas"

1. Introduction

NewLife4Drylands (LIFE20 PRE/IT/000007) deals with land degradation processes, of which desertification is one aspect, and considers restoration as a process. Both processes must be monitored resorting to status and trend indicators and time thresholds to ensure that ecosystems achieve or maintain a healthy state or a good condition, which is key requirement to secure the sustainability of human activities and human well-being.

One of the main impacts of land degradation is that affecting the supply of ecosystem services (ES) which can be partially or completely compromised by degradation processes. In order to monitor over time the supply of ES and their response to ongoing degradation processes, it is necessary to assess and map ES periodically, resorting to fast and low-cost tools which allow to detect changes and trends in ES provision. To this goal, remote sensing (RS) represents an extremely valuable source of data which are spatially explicit, cost effective, rapidly assessed, available for almost any area around the globe, multi-temporal and at a spatial resolution which is feasible for most ES assessment applications.

The number of RS applications to ES assessment and mapping has increased significantly in the last decade and have addressed mostly provisioning services, such as timber and food production, and regulatory services: air quality, climate regulation, extreme events prevention and control, waste treatment, erosion control, and soil fertility (Anayu et al., 2012). A systematic review of literature on remote sensing of ecosystem services is provide by de Araujo Barbosa et al. (2015) who concluded that data and products provided by RS alone have not the capabilities to assess and map effectively the full range of ecosystem services, and therefore there is the indeed for integrated approach through the fusion of remotely sensed data with information from other sources (del Río-Mena et al., 2023; Awada et al., 2022; del Río-Mena et al., 2020; Thomas et al., 2020; Zhang, 2010; Zhu et al., 2018).

Data and products provided by RS for ES assessment and mapping include, among many others, land cover maps for ecosystem extent, indicators of ecosystem conditions, phenology, NDVI (normalized Difference Vegetation Index), EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index), Leaf Area Index, NPP (Net Primary Production), terrain attributes such as slope and elevation, damage impacts and ecosystem structure (LiDAR, SAR). These data and products provide spatially explicit and time-variant information that can be successfully used as proxy to assess and map ecosystem service supply and their variation over time .

In general, the assessment of ecosystem services via RS-based indices (RSI) is an indirect process. This means that the remotely sensed information is used as a proxy for some kind of variable (e.g., soil mass retained by vegetation) which in turn is used as a proxy for the actual ecosystem service (e.g., erosion control). According to literature, two different approaches are commonly used to estimate in bio-physical units the variables which underpin the provision of a given ecosystem service. The first category directly uses the remotely sensed spectral signature or derived composite indexes and includes statistical regressions and/or radiative transfer models. The second approach uses remote sensing data to generate land use/land cover classifications which are then linked to ecosystem services supply and used as input for physically based models of ecosystem services assessment.

2. Ecosystem services assessment and mapping: the NL4DL approach and workflow

Within the framework of the NL4DL LIFE preparatory project, the purpose of ES assessment is to integrate ground data and existing thematic data layers with remote sensing observations to account for temporal variations in ecosystem services supply with reference to a baseline.

Action 2 (lead by CNR IIA, Bari Unit) provided a set of selected well-known indicators from remote sensing along with the technical procedure for their extraction from open satellite data, at a local scale, for each case study area (Tarantino et al., 2021). The selection of indicators has been carried out based on scientific and technical literature, consortium members' expertise and discussions with the Advisory Board, and provided a list of 26 RS-based indicators describing the status of vegetation (11 indicators), water (3 indicators), and soil (3 indicators) and the intensity of degradation process (DP), i.e., wildfires (2 indicators), soil salinity (5 indicators) and drought (2 indicators). The assessment and mapping of ES provision and DP intensity over time resorts to some of these RSI combined with time invariant features of the case study areas. As the case study areas (Figure 1) have been described in detail in previous project deliverable reports (Tarantino et al., 2021; Tarantino et al., 2023), only the information necessary for the contextualization of ecosystem dynamics and degradation processes will be provided in this report.

Figure 3. Location of the six NL4DL case study areas.

The approach developed within the framework of NL4DL is tailored to tackle situations with limited or no availability of measured ground data in the case study areas (CSA), which exclude the possibility to resort to data fusion techniques. Nevertheless, it would provide a low-cost spatially explicit methodology, that could be rapidly implemented in almost any area, providing multi-temporal outputs at a spatial resolution which is sufficient for most ES and DP assessment applications. Given the development of cloud-based geospatial analysis platforms which allows users to retrieve satellite images for any target area and for specific time intervals, the NL4DL RSI-based approach to ES and DP assessment and mapping relies on the remote sensing

indices (RSI) computed for any convenient time interval retrieved via Google Earth Engine (GEE, Gorelick et al., 2017; <https://earthengine.google.com/>).

In agreement with the project partners responsible for the CSAs, the assessment in four out of six NL4DL areas has focused on three ecosystem services: i) *Above ground C stock (AGCS)*, ii) *Soil erosion control (SEC)*, and iii) *Above ground biomass (AGB)*. The first two are regulating services, while the third is a provision service (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018).

Given the lack of measured ground data the following were taken as proxies for the target ecosystem services: i) MODIS (MOD17) net primary production (kg C m^{-2} , Running et al., 2004) for above ground C stock (Das et al., 2023); ii) RUSLE based amount of soil mass retained by vegetation computed as the difference between potential and actual soil erosion ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$, Panagos et al., 2022) for soil erosion control; and iii) Sentinel2 Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI, Rouse et al., 1974) for above ground (plant biomass (Santin-Janin et al., 2009). For two case study areas, namely Nestos River Delta in NE Greece and Palo laziale, in central Italy, being both in lowland coastal areas the assessment of SEC as regulating service was of no relevance to the goal of the analyses. It was then decided to focus on two different degradation processes which are currently posing threats to the local ecosystem: soil salinization in Nestos River Delta, and vegetation cover decline in Palo laziale due to constantly increasing aridity conditions.

```
NDVI2015_Nestos
Get Link Save Run Reset Apps
Imports (1 entry)
  var polygon: Table projects/ee-ungarofabrizio-1/assets/Nestos_EPSG2100_clip
1 var shp = ee.FeatureCollection (polygon);
2 Map.addLayer(shp, {}, 'My Polygon');
3
4
5 //Sentinel 2 RSI NL4DL Nestos River Delta
6 var S2_collection = ee.ImageCollection("COPERNICUS/S2")
7   .filterBounds(polygon)
8   .filterDate('2022-01-01', '2022-12-31')
9   .filterMetadata('CLOUDY_PIXEL_PERCENTAGE', 'less_than', 10);
10
11 print(S2_collection);
12 var S2_mosaic = S2_collection.median().clip(polygon);
13 var S2_display = {bands:['B2', 'B3', 'B4', 'B8', 'B8A', 'B11'], min:0, max:3000};
14 Map.addLayer (S2_mosaic, S2_display, "S2_Image");
15
16
17 //Selecting and displaying the composite's bands
18
19 Map.centerObject(polygon);
20 var blue = S2_mosaic.select ('B2');
21   Map.addLayer (blue, {min:0, max:3000}, "S2_Blue", false);
22
23 var green = S2_mosaic.select ('B3');
24   Map.addLayer (green, {min:0, max:3000}, "S2_Green", false);
25
26 var red = S2_mosaic.select ('B4');
27   Map.addLayer (red, {min:0, max:3000}, "S2_Red", false);
28
29 var IR = S2_mosaic.select ('B8');
30   Map.addLayer (IR, {min:0, max:3000}, "S2_IR", false);
31
32 var IRn = S2_mosaic.select ('B8A');
33   Map.addLayer (IRn, {min:0, max:3000}, "S2_IRn", false);
34
35 var SWIR = S2_mosaic.select ('B11');
36   Map.addLayer (SWIR, {min:0, max:3000}, "SWIR", false);
37   Map.centerObject(polygon);
38
```

Figure 2. GEE JavaScript console: setting the target area and the composite's bands to extract.

Using GEE JavaScript API at the URL <https://code.earthengine.google.com/> the user can import the area of interest as ESRI format shape file (EPSG 4326) and select the time frame for the

extraction of the required spectral bands which are further used to calculate RSI, e.g. NDVI (Figure 2). For each band it is possible to specify not only the time frame of interest and the % of cloud cover tolerance, but also the statistics relevant to the goal of the assessment (e.g. median value, mean value, maximum). Within the NL4DL ES/DP assessment and mapping, raster maps of yearly median values of RS images have been extracted for each CSA, considering the time frame 2015-2022 (8 years) and setting <10% the cloud pixel percentage. The following spectral bands have been extracted for each year (median value): **B2** (blue, central wavelength 490 nm), **B3** (green, central wavelength 560 nm), **B4** (red, central wavelength 665 nm), **B8** (IR, central wavelength 842 nm), **B8A** (IRn, central wavelength 865 nm) and **B11** (SWIR, central wavelength 1610 nm). The first four have a 10m spatial resolution, while the last two have a 20m spatial resolution. The above listed bands have been used within the GEE java script to calculate the following RSIs (Figure 3): **NDVI**, **NDBSI** (Normalised Difference Bare Soil Index), **NDSI** (Normalised Difference Soil Index), **BI** (Bare Index), **SoSI1** (Soil Salinity Index 1), **SoSI2** (Soil Salinity Index 2), **SoSI3** (Soil Salinity Index 3), **SASI** (Soil Adjusted Salinity Index), **SOSA** (Soil SALinity), and **NDWI** (Normalised Difference Water Index),

Figure 3. GEE JavaScript console: example of RSIs computation for 2022 in the Nestos River delta CSA.

Given the different spatial resolution of the available raster layers for the three proxies, i.e. 500 m for MOD17, 100 m for soil erosion and 20 to 10m for the extracted spectral signatures, there is the need to rescale the first two to the desired resolution of the final ES maps resorting to downscale techniques (Li et al., 2024;). To downscale the contents of RS imagery (e.g., NPP) or of raster maps from different sources (e.g., actual and potential soil erosion raster maps) the information on the relation between spatial data at different resolutions was used to calibrate regression models (Atkinson, 2013). Examples of downscaling to estimate ES from RS are given by Ungaro et al. (2021) and Schwartz et al. (2022) .The desired target resolution is different depending on the size of the CSA: it was set to 25m for El Nublo II-Tamadaba , Alta Murgia, Nestos River delta and Asterousia, and 10 m for El Bruc and Palo Laziale. For the 25m resolution, the upscaling of RSI from the original resolution was performed resorting to R scripts R Core Team (2021) which also allows for the alignment of all the necessary raster maps.

Figure 4. Flowchart illustrating the steps of ES services assessment and mapping resorting to Remote Sensing Indices and time invariant covariates.

The complete data flow and the steps that lead to the final mapping outputs is depicted in Figure 4. The downscaling resorted to stepwise multiple linear regressions (MLR) calibrated over gridded data points which were used to sample the proxies' raster layers for the selected baseline years along with the raster maps of predictor variables available at the target resolutions of the final ES/DP maps. The predictors were chosen among several RSI indices (time dependent) among those identified by action A2, and terrain, soil, and landscape attributes (time invariant) based on correlations analysis. Using the MLR calibrated for the ES/DP proxies, it is possible to estimate indicators of potential ES supply for all the other years of the considered time series up to 2022 using the annual median values for all the RSI predictors, and to assess relative difference with reference to the selected baseline. In the case of AGB, though, the comparison with the baseline is straightforward as the indicator is based only on NDVI which is already available at the target resolution.

A different reference baseline year for ES assessment has been considered for the different areas (e.g., 2016 in Tifaracás and 2019 in El Bruc, 2015 in Asterousia), so to use RSI from the Copernicus-Sentinel2 repository which are available from 2015 (<https://scihub.copernicus.eu/>). The time series considered for ES assessment and mapping changes from site to site in agreement with the events that occurred and triggered land degradation processes and the possible recovery: for example, it is 2015-2022 in El Bruc and Asterousia, 2016-2022 in Tifaracás.

Although in the case of AGCS and SEC the outcomes can be expressed in terms of biophysical units, respectively Mg C ha^{-1} and $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$, it is preferred to standardize the values resorting to an interval normalization (Wu et al., 2013) as follows:

$$I_{\text{AGCS-20yy}} = (\text{AGCS}_{\text{yy}} - \text{min}_{\text{baseline}}) / (\text{MAX}_{\text{baseline}} - \text{min}_{\text{baseline}})$$

where min and MAX are the minimum and the maximum value observed over the study area for the baseline year. In this way the ES indicator values would range from 0 to 1 for the baseline year, while for the other years they might fall outside this interval depending on the data range observed each year, if so data <0 or >1 are set equal to 0 and 1 respectively.

Using standardised values, therefore, it is possible to compare, and then map, different services or the same services across regions or over time. In this way indicator values normalized resorting to the baseline relative scales, would range from 0 to 1, where 0 represents no relevant ecosystem service supply. Lack of relevance does not mean that a given ecosystem service is not provided but rather that its level of supply is relatively the lowest with respect to the service provided by other spatial units within a given area. At the other end of the scale, 1 represent the maximum level of ecosystem service supplied by a given area.

The proposed methodology allows to assess and map the values of selected ES/DP indicators along with their relative changes with respect to the baseline years. The integration of time dependent predictors from remote sensing in a spatially explicit digital mapping workflow allows to visualize where the changes occur and their relative magnitudes.

3. Spanish case study areas: El Bruc and El Nublo-Tamadaba

The two Spanish case study areas are in Gran Canaria, El Nublo II-Tamadaba (ca 265 km²) and in Catalonia, El Bruc (ca 12.9 km²).

Figure 5. Different landscapes and vegetation formations in El Nublo II-Tamadaba (Photos: F. Ungaro).

El Nublo II-Tamadaba (Figure 5), in the Gran Canaria Biosphere Reserve includes two Natura 2000 Areas: a Site of Community Importance (SCI) and a Special Area for Conservation (SAC). The area presents an average elevation of 873 m (ranging from 0 to 1872 m). Inside this large area we can find desertification processes triggered by severe herbivory (wild goats), wildfires (fire event in 2019, ca. 13000 ha affected) and the arid climate. Average annual rainfall is below 200 mm, although in recent years it has not exceeded 100 mm, with dry periods without rain longer than 10 months, making it very difficult to reforest the area to establish a vegetation cover to protect the soil from erosion. Although the high stoniness of the soil means that it is not particularly vulnerable to erosion, the low vegetation cover, the steep slope of the

hillsides and the severe rainfall events favor erosion processes. These processes lead to the loss of fertile soil, making it even more difficult to establish vegetation cover.

Figure 6. Vegetation recovery in the fire affected area, land degradation and patch of agricultural land use in El Bruc (Photos: F. Ungaro)

El Bruc site (Figure 6), located at an average elevation of 494 m (range 355-585 m) has a Mediterranean climate, with a precipitation average of 666 mm/y, 46 average days of rain, and more than 3 dry months. Due to this factor, as well as the high recurrence of forest fires, there are areas with low natural regeneration and affected by concentrated and diffuse erosion processes. The area went under a natural fire in 2015 which burnt ca. 1235 ha. A large part of the burnt forest was Aleppo pine (*Pinus halepensis*), which had already suffered a fire in 1986. The pines – which do not have a resprouting strategy, but germinate – are having a modest and variable regeneration throughout the area, possibly due to the intense drought that affected the area, especially in the years immediately after the fire. The site represents a protection and

connection corridor for the Montserrat-Roques Blanques-riu Llobregat SCI, an area with a high touristic, aesthetic, and ecological value. In the framework of the LIFE The Green Link project (<https://thegreenlink.eu/project-areas/cataluna/>) more than 20 ha of forest and agricultural species were planted to recover the most degraded areas and increase the recovery of the agrosilvopastoral mosaic, which helps to reduce the vulnerability of the area to future forest fires. Table 1 summarizes the settings of ES assessment and mapping for the two Spanish CSAs.

CSA	Area	ES	Type of ES	CICES v1.5	Proxy	Units	Input res.	Output res.	Baseline	Time interval	EPSG
El Nublo II - Tamadaba	265 km ²	AGCS	Regulating	2.1.1.2	MOD17 NPP	C Mg/ha	500 m	25 m	2016	2016-2022	32628
		SEC	Regulating	2.2.1.1/2.2.1.3	RUSLE (PSE-ASE)	Mg /ha /y	100 m	25 m	2016	2016-2022	32628
		AGB	Provision	1.1.5.x/1.1.1.x	NDVI Sentinel2	-	20 m	25 m	2016	2016-2022	32628
El Bruc	13 km ²	AGCS	Regulating	2.1.1.2	MOD17 NPP	C Mg/ha	500 m	10 m	2019	2015-2022	25831
		SEC	Regulating	2.2.1.1/2.2.1.3	RUSLE (PSE-ASE)	Mg /ha /y	100 m	10 m	2019	2015-2022	25831
		AGB	Provision	1.1.5.x/1.1.1.x	NDVI Sentinel2	-	20 m	10 m	2019	2015-2022	25831

Table 1. Setting of ES assessment for the Spanish CSAs.

In order to estimate and map AGCS in the two sites, MODIS17 NPP images were retrieved resorting to GEE for the period 2015-2022. Yearly mean values and their 95% confidence intervals are shown in the box & whisker plot in Figure 7, where the drop in C stock due to fire events and prolonged droughts is clearly evident and with distinct patterns in the two CSAs, as evident is also the recovery of NPP values following the fire events in both sites.

Figure 7. NPP (kg C m⁻²) yearly means for El Nublo-Tamadaba (left) and El Bruc (right).

The MLR equation calibrated to downscale NPP values of the baseline year from the original 500m resolution to the finer target resolution, have the following form for El Nublo-Tamadaba (N = 1601, reference year 2016, resolution 25 m):

$$npp_{2016} = 2.277567 + (8.117397 * ndvi_{2016}) + (0.003675 * dem) + (-0.001544 * swir_{2016}) + (0.002542 * ir_{2016}) + (-0.087380 * twi) + (-0.004252 * chanetdis) + (-0.000783 * vdepth) + (0.492133 * slope) + (-0.039007 * aspect) + (0.822895 * relslopos) + (-0.001254 * red_{2016})$$

while in the case of El Bruc (N = 327, resolution 10m), for which 2019 was selected as reference year, it has the following form:

$$npp_{2019} = 9.73621 - 3.29148 * NDBSI_{2019} - 0.00659 * elevation - 0.01854 * valleyDepth + 0.57231 * NDSI_{2019} + 0.00063 * IR_{2019} - 0.00161 * red_{2019} + 0.00220 * blue_{2019} - 0.00037 * Aspect$$

Figure 8. Observed vs estimated NPP raster maps for El Nublo-Tamadaba (top) and El Bruc (bottom).

Figure 8 shows the observed and estimated NPP maps along with the regularly gridded sampling points used in the two cases to sample the rasters layers of target and predictor variables, while figure 9 shows the scatterplots between observed and estimated NPP values for the two Spanish ND4DL sites.

Figure 9. Observed vs estimated NPP (Mg C/ha) for El Nublo-Tamadaba (left) and El Bruc (right).

Figure 10. Annual NPP values (Mg C/ha) estimates for El Nublo II-Tamadba site (2017-2022),

By applying the MLR equations calibrated for the baseline reference year, the annual NPP values (Mg C/ha) were computed over the area of interest for the two sites of El Nublo II-Tamadaba (Figure 10) and El Bruc (Figure 11), at the resolution of 25 and 10 m respectively.

Figure 11. Annual NPP values (Mg C/ha) estimates for El Bruc site (2015-2022),

The estimation of the annual values for the SEC indicator resorted to the following MLR equations, calibrate for the baseline years, who provided annual estimates of the soil mass potentially retained by vegetation expressed as Mg/ha/y:

$$7.6161418 + 0.003483 * SWIR_{2016} - (0.0071395 * IR_{2016}) - (36.3725232 * BI_{2016}) + (0.0021574 * IRn_{2016}) + (0.025464 * ChaNetDis) + (28.968938 * Slope) + (0.553225 * LSfactor) + (0.263609 * TWI)$$

for the El Nublo II-Tamadaba site (N = 25569, reference year 2016, resolution 25 m), and

$$RetSoilMass_{2019} = 1383.643 + (74.041 * NDVI_{2019}) - (107.006 * NDBSI_{2019}) - (2.465 * Elevation) + - (22.578 * BI_{2019}) + (4.936 * Slope)$$

for the El Bruc site (N = 704, reference year 2019, resolution 10 m).

Figure 12. Observed vs estimated retained soil mass for the reference year for El Nublo-Tamadaba (top) and El Bruc (bottom).

Figure 12 shows the observed and estimated soilmass retained by vegetation maps along with the regularly gridded sampling points used in the two cases to sample the rasters layers of target and predictor variables, while figure 9 shows the scatterplots between observed and estimated soil retained mass for the baseline year in the two Spanish ND4DL sites.

Figure 13. Observed vs estimated soil mass retained by vegetation for El Nublo-Tamadaba (left, baseline 2016) and El Bruc (right, baseline 2019).

Figure 14. Annual soil mass retained by vegetation (Mg /ha/y) estimated for El Nublo II-Tamadaba site (2017-2022),

By applying the MLR equations calibrated for the baseline reference year, the annual NPP values (Mg C/ha) were computed over the area of interest for the two sites of El Nublo II-Tamadaba (Figure 14) and El Bruc (Figure 12).

Figure 15. Annual soil mass retained by vegetation (Mg/ha/y) estimated for El Bruc site (2015-2022),

As changes in soil mass retained by vegetation with respect to the baseline year might be hard to detect visually in the maps in figure 14 and 15, figures 16 and 17 displays the annual differences with respect to the selected baseline for El Nublo II-Tamadaba and El Bruc respectively.

Figure 15. Annual differences with respect to the baseline year (2015) in soil mass retained by vegetation (Mg /ha/y) estimated for El Nublo II-Tamadaba site (2017-2022),

Figure 16. Annual differences with respect to the baseline year (2019) in soil mass retained by vegetation (Mg /ha/y) estimated for El Bruc (2015-2022),

In order to compute and map the indicators of ES potential supply, all the yearly estimates presented in Figures 10 and 11 were standardized with respect to the reference baseline year selected for each site. This was also done for the annual median NDVI maps retrieved via GEE, so that the three indicators could be compared over the same 0-1 scale.

Figure 17. El Nublo II-Tamadaba: maps of the ES indicators (AGCS top, SEC middle, AGB bottom) for the baseline year 2016 (left), 2020 (centre) and 2022 (right).

For the Canary island site Figure 17 displays the maps of the three indicators for three years (2016, 2020 and 2022). In the indicators maps the red color represents the maximum potential provision of any given ES (i.e. values close to 1), while at the other end of the scale the blue color highlights the areas where the potential ES supply is at its minimum across the site (i.e., values close to 0). With respect to the baseline year, at the El Nublo II-Tamadaba site the trend observed for the three selected indicators of ES potential supply is constantly negative along the time series (Table 2), with two negative peaks affecting the supply of all services. The first occurs

between 2019 and 2020 after the wildfires which affected the north-est part of the area destroying more than 30% of the Canarian pine (*Pinus canariensis*) forest and resulted in a drop -15.0% in AGCS, -2.35% in SEC and -10,5% in AGB with respect to the reference baseline year (2016). The second negative peak, more pronounced, occurred in 2022, due to prolonged drought conditions and lead to a drop of -18.4% in AGCS, -4.9% in SEC and -17.2% in AGB with respect to the reference baseline year. In this second case it is the entire area to be affected, and the losses of ESs supply are widespread and lot localized as observed for 2020.

The 2022 drought in Europe is considered a compound drought and heatwaves event (CDHW) and is reported as one of the most severe in recent history (Tripahty et al., 2023), affecting large parts of the continent. The event was particularly intense over the Iberian Peninsula, France, Italy, Northwest Balkans, Germany, the Netherlands, Poland, and Scandinavia (Faranda et al., 2023).

AGCS	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	1.044	1.096	1.070	1.008	1.038	1.033
Mean	0.402	0.378	0.399	0.376	0.342	0.391	0.328
Min	0.000	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004
Stdev	0.103	0.098	0.105	0.101	0.085	0.098	0.056
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	0.0%	-6.0%	-0.7%	-6.5%	-15.0%	-2.8%	-18.4%
<i>Previous year</i>		-6.0%	5.7%	-5.8%	-9.2%	14.4%	-16.1%
SEC	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	1.006	0.996	1.019	1.012	1.013	0.984
Mean	0.288	0.281	0.284	0.285	0.282	0.286	0.274
Min	0.000	-0.004	0.001	-0.001	0.000	0.003	-0.014
Stdev	0.109	0.105	0.106	0.107	0.106	0.110	0.103
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	0.0%	-2.5%	-1.4%	-1.0%	-2.3%	-0.7%	-4.9%
<i>Previous year</i>		-2.5%	1.1%	0.4%	-1.3%	1.6%	-4.2%
AGB	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	1.002	0.993	0.975	0.930	0.977	0.796
Mean	0.545	0.525	0.543	0.524	0.487	0.529	0.451
Min	0.000	0.105	0.076	0.072	0.008	-0.013	0.179
Stdev	0.103	0.098	0.105	0.101	0.085	0.098	0.056
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	0.0%	-3.6%	-0.3%	-3.8%	-10.5%	-2.8%	-17.2%
<i>Previous year</i>		-3.6%	3.4%	-3.5%	-6.9%	8.6%	-14.8%

Table 2. El Nublo II-Tamadaba site: ES Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2016)

For the Catalonia site Figure 18 displays the maps of the three indicators for three years (2015, 2019, 2022). Again, in the indicators maps the orange to red color represent the maximum potential provision of any given ES (i.e. values close to 1), while at the other end of the scale the green to blue color highlights the areas where the potential ES supply is at its minimum across the site (i.e., values close to 0).

Table 3 summarize the results for the three ES indicators in El Bruc respectively in term of ES indicator mean values and its relative changes with respect to the baseline year adopted for the assessment. From the values in the tables, it can be observed that in the case of El Bruc the most relevant changes occur in 2015 and 2016, after the forest fire and again in 2022 as result of the prolonged drought that affected most of Europe.

Figure 18. El Bruc: maps of the ES indicators (AGCS top, SEC middle, AGB bottom) for the baseline year 2019 (left), 2015 (centre) and 2022 (right).

As related to the effects of the 2015 wildfire, the potential supply of ES exhibits a drop ranging from -18.0% for SEC to- 55.8% for AGCS and to .70.5% in AGB. The effect of the fire are evident also in 2016 and 2017 were the trend keeps on being negative for the three indicators of ES supply, but between 2018 and 2020 the trend became positivity with evidence of ecosystem recovery up to the pre-fire condition (see NPP values in Figure 7)..

AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.051	0.000	0.042	0.000	0.016
Mean	0.175	0.249	0.293	0.431	0.395	0.465	0.369	0.34134
Min	-0.311	-0.036	-0.038	0.013	0.000	0.006	-0.013	-0.043
Stdev	0.151	0.131	0.139	0.158	0.155	0.167	0.150	0.138
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	-55.8%	-37.0%	-25.8%	8.9%	0.0%	17.6%	-6.6%	-13.7%
<i>Previous year</i>		42.6%	17.7%	46.9%	-8.2%	17.6%	-20.6%	-7.6%

SEC	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.981	0.999	0.999	1.000	0.999	0.999	0.999
Mean	0.288	0.324	0.332	0.358	0.352	0.366	0.348	0.33095
Min	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Stdev	0.109	0.165	0.169	0.171	0.171	0.172	0.170	0.167
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	-18.0%	-8.0%	-5.6%	1.8%	0.0%	3.8%	-1.1%	-6.0%
<i>Previous year</i>		12.2%	2.6%	7.9%	-1.8%	3.8%	-4.8%	-4.9%

AGB	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.863	0.973	0.971	1.013	1.000	1.093	0.969	0.570
Mean	0.141	0.303	0.350	0.513	0.477	0.562	0.461	0.23217
Min	-0.311	-0.036	-0.038	0.013	0.000	0.006	-0.013	-0.043
Stdev	0.129	0.123	0.118	0.137	0.138	0.157	0.126	0.068
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	-70.5%	-36.5%	-26.7%	7.5%	0.0%	17.8%	-3.3%	-51.3%
<i>Previous year</i>		115.1%	15.4%	46.7%	-7.0%	17.8%	-17.9%	-49.7%

Table 3. El Bruc site: ES Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2019)

In 2021 the trend becomes negative again with a slight decrease with respect to the reference year (-6.6% AGCS, 1.1% SEC and .3.3% AGB), but it is again in 2022 that the drought effect leads to a generalized decrease of ES supply over the entire site, with a drop of -13.7% in AGCS, -6.0% in Sec and -51.3% in AGB,

During the Spring and Summer of 2022 all over Europe temperatures exceeded 2.5°C above normal, and severe droughts persisted from May to August. Using a Bayesian approach, Tripathy et al. (2023) estimated the return period (RP) for the 2022 CDHW event, which was unprecedented in Northern Italy, Iberian Peninsula, and western parts of France, with RPs of 354, 420, and 280 years, respectively. The reduced soil moisture due to precipitation deficits and high temperatures contributed to the persistence and severity of drought, creating a positive feedback loop where dry soils led to even drier conditions.

Figure 19. Relative changes in ESs potential supply in 2022 with reference to the selected baseline (2016) at El Nublo II-Tamadaba site.

Given the magnitude of changes in ESs potential supply in the time period considered, Figures 19 and 20 show the spatial distribution of the relative difference with respect to the baseline for the year characterised by the major drop in ES supply, i.e., 2022 in El Nublo II-Tamadaba and 2015 in E Bruc.

Figure 20. Relative changes in ESs potential supply in 2015 with reference to the selected baseline (2019) at El Bruc site.

4. Greek case study areas: Asterousia and Nestos River delta

The Asterousia mountain range is in the Heraklion Prefecture of Crete, separating the Messara Plain from the Libyan Sea. The average elevation is 370 m a.s.l., with its maximum at Mt. Kofinas (1231 m a.s.l.) The climate of the area is characterized as sub-humid Mediterranean with humid and relatively cold winters and dry and warm summers. The soils are highly degraded due to erosion with exposed bedrock in several places. Although the natural vegetation in Asterousia shows a capacity for succession to higher forms, the area is overgrazed during the winter months preventing such succession. In addition, climate, with long and dry summer and high evapotranspiration rates, favours desertification due to water scarcity and droughts.

Figure 21. Landscapes, land uses and land degradation in Asterousia (Photos: F. Ungaro).

In recent decades Asterousia has seen a widespread change in land uses driven mainly by the abandonment of traditional cultivation on drywall terraces, often replaced by intensive olive orchards, the expansion of road networks and infrastructure serving tourism development and renewable energy sources (RES) projects. Another crucial change has been the overgrazing of virtually all grasslands due to the steep increase of livestock numbers and the abandonment of the traditional extensive animal farming model driven by the current CAP subsidies policy. These human pressures coupled with the effects of climate change contribute to the increase of soil loss due to water and wind erosion resulting in the degradation of productive arable land, decline of vegetation cover, loss of biodiversity and its functioning, habitat and landscape modification.

The Nestos site is the largest remaining riparian forest in the Mediterranean area, protected within the 'Delta Nestou' Natura 2000 site. This is an area of great ornithological value, but in past decades has been severely reduced in size, from over 12,000 ha in the early 1920s to merely 2,000 ha in fragments along both banks of the river nowadays. Habitats and species in both Natura 2000 sites face several serious threats, including shrub expansion and invasive species encroachment, eutrophication, and inappropriate forest and water management. These pressures are related both to direct and indirect human actions which expose the forest ecosystems to multiple stress factors.

CSA	Area	ES	Type of ES	CICES v1.5	Proxy	Units	Input res.	Output res.	Baseline	Time interval	EPSG
Asterousia	423 km ²	AGCS	Regulating	2.1.1.2	MOD17 NPP	C Mg/ha	500 m	25 m	2015	2015-2022	2100
		SEC	Regulating	2.2.1.1/2.2.1.3	RUSLE (PSE-ASE)	Mg /ha /y	100 m	25 m	2015	2015-2022	2100
		AGB	Provision	1.1.5.x/1.1.1.x	NDVI Sentinel2	-	20 m	25 m	2015	2015-2022	2100
Nestos	378 km ²	AGCS	Regulating	2.1.1.2	MOD17 NPP	C Mg/ha	500 m	25 m	2016	2015-2022	2100
		AGB	Provision	1.1.5.x/1.1.1.x	NDVI Sentinel2	-	20 m	25 m	2015	2015-2022	2100
		SoS	Degradation	n.a.	SoSI2 - TWI -DtoC	-	20 m	25 m	2016	2015-2022	2100

Table 4. Setting of ES assessment for the Greek CSAs.

Table 4 summarizes the settings of ES assessment and mapping for the two Greek CSAs. In Asterousia CSA the goal of the analysis is to provide annual estimates (2015 - 2022) of potential ecosystem services supply not only over the entire area (ca 423 km²) but also focusing on four specific areas (Figure 22): Pegadaikion (ca 71.7 km²) , Miamous (ca 40.2 km²) , Paranimfi (ca 21.4 km²) and Xondrous (ca 29.0 km²).

Figure 22. The four focus areas along the Asterousia range.

To estimate and map AGCS in the two sites, MODIS17 NPP were retrieved resorting to GEE for the period 2015-2022, and the 500m resolution NPP rasters were sampled (grid 500 m) in order to provide the basis for downscaling to 25m resolution via calibration of stepwise MLR (Figure 22). For the Asterousia site, the MLR to downscale MODIS17 NPP to 25 m resolution as the following form (N =2340):

$$\text{NPP}_{2015} = 8.894154 + (-0.001252 * \text{SWIR}_{2015}) + (2.786388 * \text{NDVI}_{2015}) + (0.002757 * \text{Irn}_{2015}) + (-0.001525 * \text{IR}_{2015}) + (-0.001250 * \text{BLUE}_{2015}) + (-0.001330 * \text{DEM}) + (0.000001 * \text{ModifiedCatchmentArea}) + (-0.007344 * \text{ValleyDepth}) + (-0.021224 * \text{Slope})$$

while the following is the algorithm calibrated for Nestos (N = 674):

$$\text{NPP}_{2016} = 4742.37 + (1559.06 * \text{NDVI}_{2016}) + (-0.272 * \text{SOSI2}_{2016}) + (-838.26 * \text{NDBSI}_{2016}) + (13.346 * \text{DEM}) + (0.015 * \text{ModifiedCatchmentArea}) + (-1539.09 * \text{CatchmentSlope})$$

Figure 23 shows the observed and estimated NPP maps along with the regularly gridded sampling points used in the two cases to sample the rasters layers of target and predictor variables, while figure 24 shows the scatterplots between observed and estimated NPP values for the two Greek ND4DL sites.

Figure 23. Observed and estimated NPP raster maps at 100m (left) and 25m (right) resolution for Asterousia (top) and Nestos River delta (bottom) for the baseline years.

Figure 24. Observed vs estimated NPP (Mg C/ha) for Asterousia (left) and Nestos (right).

By applying the MLR equations calibrated for the baseline reference year, i.e., by changing the annua media values of the RSIs, the annual NPP values (Mg C/ha) were estimated over the area of interest for the two sites of Asterousia (Figure 25) and Nestos (Figure 26) at 25 m resolution.

Figure 25. Annual NPP values (Mg C/ha) estimates for Asterousia site (range 0.07 – 8.5 Mg C/ha).

Figure 26. Annual NPP values (Mg C/ha) estimates for Nestos site (range 3.6 – 8.1 Mg C/ha).

The soil erosion control (by vegetation) regulating service was assessed and mapped only in the Asterousia site, resorting to the same methodological approach implemented for the Spanish CSAs. The MLR calibrated for the baseline year (2015) to downscale the estimated soil mass retained by vegetation from 100 to 25 m resolution (Figure 27) has the following form (N = 40794):

$$2.619557 - (.000413 * \text{Red2015}) - (.930363 * \text{NDBSI2015}) + (0.000488 * \text{SWIR2015}) - (.586093 * \text{NDVI2015}) - (.000461 * \text{IRn2015}) + (0.000473 * \text{Blue2015}) + (0.000063 * \text{dem}) + (0.008793 * \text{slope}) + (0.000988 * \text{valley depth}) - (.0000004 * \text{catch area mod.}) - (.1133779 * \text{sagaTWI}) + (1.711844 * \text{catch slope}) + (0.000001 * \text{catchment area})$$

Figure 27. Observed and MLR estimated soil mass retained by vegetation (log scale) for Asterousia (baseline year 2015).

In both sites the AGB provisioning service was estimated adopting the baseline NDVI as proxy and resorting to a 0-1 interval standardization it made possible to compare the indicators and their relative changes with respect to the baseline.

For the whole Asterousia site the relative changes with respect to 2015 baseline for **AGCS regulating service** are summarised in Table 5, while Tabel 6 report the results for the same indicator In the four focus areas along the mountain range.

AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.978	0.984	0.984	0.987	0.985	0.974	0.803
Mean	0.599	0.573	0.589	0.578	0.595	0.594	0.570	0.410
Min	0.000	-0.066	-0.087	-0.107	-0.058	-0.091	-0.110	-0.275
Stdev	0.094	0.090	0.093	0.092	0.095	0.092	0.091	0.093
<i>Baseline 2015</i>	0.00%	-4.30%	-1.68%	-3.51%	-0.56%	-0.76%	-4.71%	-31.48%
<i>Previous year</i>		-4.3%	2.7%	-1.9%	3.1%	-0.2%	-4.0%	-28.1%

Table 5. Asterousia site: AGCS Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015) .

AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.978	0.984	0.984	0.987	0.985	0.974	0.803
Mean	0.580	0.545	0.558	0.548	0.573	0.559	0.542	0.377
Min	0.000	-0.066	-0.087	-0.107	-0.058	-0.091	-0.110	-0.275
Stdev	0.104	0.111	0.112	0.115	0.110	0.110	0.113	0.112
Pegaidakion								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	-6.1%	-3.7%	-5.4%	-1.2%	-3.5%	-6.5%	-35.0%
Previous year		-6.1%	2.6%	-1.8%	4.5%	-2.3%	-3.1%	-30.5%
AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.867	0.848	0.885	0.887	0.913	0.908	0.876	0.705
Mean	0.619	0.600	0.622	0.618	0.625	0.619	0.601	0.435
Min	0.335	0.285	0.305	0.314	0.307	0.321	0.309	0.026
Stdev	0.065	0.069	0.068	0.067	0.070	0.066	0.067	0.068
Miamous								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	-3.1%	0.6%	-0.1%	1.0%	0.1%	-2.9%	-29.7%
Previous year		-3.1%	3.8%	-0.7%	1.1%	-0.9%	-3.0%	-27.6%
AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.895	0.871	0.856	0.836	0.836	0.871	0.843	0.667
Mean	0.581	0.554	0.563	0.558	0.562	0.569	0.549	0.381
Min	0.295	0.255	0.266	0.276	0.248	0.258	0.255	0.075
Stdev	0.065	0.068	0.070	0.069	0.072	0.068	0.068	0.068
Paranyfom								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	-4.8%	-3.2%	-4.1%	-3.3%	-2.2%	-5.6%	-34.4%
Previous year		-4.8%	1.6%	-0.9%	0.8%	1.1%	-3.5%	-30.5%
AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.892	0.873	0.882	0.859	0.896	0.915	0.867	0.713
Mean	0.628	0.617	0.638	0.624	0.643	0.652	0.625	0.469
Min	0.303	0.278	0.293	0.293	0.307	0.307	0.297	0.121
Stdev	0.085	0.083	0.081	0.079	0.083	0.078	0.078	0.079
Xondrou								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	-1.7%	1.6%	-0.7%	2.4%	3.8%	-0.5%	-25.3%
Previous year		-1.7%	3.4%	-2.2%	3.1%	1.3%	-4.2%	-24.9%

Table 6. Asterousia focus sites: AGCS Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

With respect to the 2015 baseline, the trend in the AGCS supply for the entire area is constantly negative with modest oscillations ranging between -0.6 and -4.8% which nevertheless increase up to -31.5% in 2022. The picture though is quite different in the four focus sites, with marked decreases in AGS supply in the westernmost area, which exhibits the sharpest drop in 2022, while in the eastern areas there are also gains in ES supply either with respect to the baseline and with respect to the previous year, AGCS indicator maps for Asterousia are shown in Figure 28.

Figure 27. Annual AGCS indicator values estimates for Asterousia site. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

In the case of the Nestos site, the trend of the **AGCS regulating service** over the eight years considered for the assessment is not regular but characterized by oscillations ranging from 0.7 to -7% with respect to the baseline (2016) with a negative maximum of almost -11% occurring in 2022 (Table 7).

NPP (C t/ha)	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Mean	0.643	0.639	0.593	0.641	0.624	0.604	0.613	0.569
Min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Stdev	0.12	0.13	0.12	0.12	0.11	0.12	0.12	0.09
Baseline 2016	0.71%	0.00%	-7.20%	0.34%	-2.26%	-5.40%	-4.01%	-10.87%
Previous year		-0.71%	-7.20%	8.12%	-2.59%	-3.21%	1.47%	-7.15%

Table 7. Nestos site: AGCS indicator yearly statistics and relative changes with respect to the baseline (2016).

Figure 28. Annual AGCS indicator values estimates for Nestos site. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2016)

The trend detected in the supply of the **SEC regulating service** for the whole Asterousia sites and for the four focus areas are summarized in Tables 8 and 9 respectively.

SEC indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.958	0.962	0.965	0.960	0.957	0.960	0.956
Mean	0.473	0.473	0.472	0.471	0.451	0.454	0.453	0.443
Min	0.000	0.021	0.031	0.045	-0.025	0.012	-0.021	0.011
Stdev	0.132	0.093	0.097	0.093	0.098	0.097	0.097	0.096
<i>Baseline 2015</i>	0.00%	0.05%	-0.01%	-0.31%	-4.62%	-3.99%	-4.11%	-6.23%
<i>Previous year</i>		0.05%	-0.06%	-0.30%	-4.32%	0.65%	-0.13%	-2.21%

Table 8. Asterousia site: SEC Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

SEC indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.958	0.962	0.965	0.960	0.957	0.960	0.956
Mean	0.419	0.432	0.427	0.429	0.414	0.410	0.422	0.406
Min	0.007	0.103	0.111	0.122	0.110	0.104	0.099	0.089
Stdev	0.119	0.087	0.088	0.086	0.087	0.086	0.087	0.088
Pegaidakion								
<i>Baseline 2015</i>	0.0%	3.1%	1.9%	2.4%	-1.1%	-1.9%	0.8%	-3.0%
<i>Previous year</i>		3.1%	-1.1%	0.5%	-3.4%	-0.9%	2.8%	-3.8%

SEC indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.851	0.847	0.835	0.861	0.854	0.855	0.838
Mean	0.508	0.503	0.500	0.496	0.476	0.478	0.478	0.469
Min	0.092	0.222	0.201	0.229	0.197	0.204	0.202	0.209
Stdev	0.100	0.068	0.069	0.069	0.075	0.071	0.072	0.072
Miamous								
<i>Baseline 2015</i>	0.0%	-1.1%	-1.7%	-2.4%	-6.3%	-6.0%	-6.0%	-7.7%
<i>Previous year</i>		-1.1%	-0.7%	-0.7%	-4.0%	0.4%	0.0%	-1.8%

SEC indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.915	0.926	0.921	0.913	0.911	0.916	0.899
Mean	0.570	0.503	0.513	0.506	0.488	0.496	0.489	0.476
Min	0.104	0.187	0.173	0.184	0.119	0.163	0.143	0.119
Stdev	0.140	0.101	0.101	0.100	0.107	0.103	0.107	0.108
Paranymfom								
<i>Baseline 2015</i>	0.0%	-11.7%	-9.9%	-11.1%	-14.3%	-12.9%	-14.2%	-16.5%
<i>Previous year</i>		-11.7%	2.0%	-1.4%	-3.5%	1.6%	-1.4%	-2.8%

SEC indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.937	0.779	0.786	0.774	0.779	0.787	0.777	0.785
Mean	0.452	0.454	0.443	0.459	0.421	0.436	0.428	0.424
Min	0.000	0.021	0.031	0.045	-0.003	0.025	-0.012	0.013
Stdev	0.105	0.077	0.077	0.077	0.081	0.079	0.082	0.079
Xondrou								
<i>Baseline 2015</i>	0.0%	0.6%	-2.0%	1.6%	-6.8%	-3.4%	-5.2%	-6.0%
<i>Previous year</i>		0.6%	-2.6%	3.6%	-8.2%	3.7%	-1.9%	-0.8%

Table 9. Asterousia focus sites: SEC Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

The yearly SEC indicator maps for Asterousia are shown in Figure 29. For the whole area the trend is constant and irregularly increasingly negative from 2017 to 2022, with some relevant difference among the focus areas, among which Paranymfon shows the greatest lost in the provision of the SEC service with respect to the baseline year (-16.5%).

Figure 27. Annual SEC indicator values estimates for Asterousia site. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

Table 10 reports the annual raster statistics for the **AGB provision service** for Asterousia, while the same statistics for the four focus areas along the mountain range are reported in Table 11.

AGB indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.946	1.017	0.946	0.995	1.010	0.966	0.803
Mean	0.366	0.349	0.363	0.362	0.408	0.406	0.380	0.309
Min	0.000	-0.024	-0.040	-0.019	-0.055	-0.017	-0.017	0.056
Stdev	0.108	0.091	0.101	0.093	0.109	0.102	0.097	0.067
<i>Baseline 2015</i>	0.00%	-4.57%	-0.59%	-1.09%	11.70%	11.02%	4.09%	-15.50%
<i>Previous year</i>		-4.57%	4.17%	-0.51%	12.93%	-0.61%	-6.24%	-18.81%

Table 10. Asterousia site: AGB Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

SEC indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.987	0.924	0.959	0.923	0.985	0.979	0.945	0.670
Mean	0.406	0.349	0.372	0.360	0.414	0.409	0.367	0.300
Min	0.014	-0.024	-0.015	-0.019	-0.021	-0.017	0.012	0.083
Stdev	0.095	0.078	0.084	0.074	0.090	0.082	0.075	0.052
Pegaidakion								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	-14.1%	-8.3%	-11.4%	1.9%	0.7%	-9.7%	-26.1%
Previous year		-14.1%	6.8%	-3.4%	15.0%	-1.2%	-10.3%	-18.2%
AGB indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.948	0.863	0.911	0.864	0.946	0.941	0.898	0.649
Mean	0.351	0.302	0.332	0.341	0.380	0.375	0.353	0.277
Min	0.071	0.052	0.072	0.044	0.054	0.065	0.052	0.086
Stdev	0.085	0.073	0.082	0.080	0.088	0.084	0.078	0.053
Miamous								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	-14.1%	-5.6%	-3.0%	8.1%	6.6%	0.3%	-21.3%
Previous year		-14.1%	9.9%	2.9%	11.4%	-1.3%	-5.9%	-21.5%
AGB indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.862	0.946	0.948	0.946	0.990	0.938	0.965	0.743
Mean	0.299	0.336	0.321	0.339	0.368	0.366	0.355	0.299
Min	0.006	0.072	0.089	0.101	0.105	0.116	0.089	0.104
Stdev	0.081	0.079	0.074	0.076	0.084	0.081	0.078	0.060
Paranyfom								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	12.5%	7.6%	13.7%	23.3%	22.6%	18.8%	0.25%
Previous year		12.5%	-4.3%	5.6%	8.5%	-0.5%	-3.1%	-15.6%
SEC indicator	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	0.928	0.977	0.920	0.983	1.010	0.966	0.759
Mean	0.423	0.411	0.448	0.410	0.489	0.480	0.462	0.364
Min	0.053	-0.021	-0.001	0.077	0.006	0.075	0.044	0.073
Stdev	0.126	0.109	0.117	0.116	0.120	0.112	0.109	0.071
Xondrou								
Baseline 2015	0.0%	-2.9%	5.8%	-3.1%	15.5%	13.5%	9.3%	-14.0%
Previous year		-2.9%	9.0%	-8.4%	19.2%	-1.7%	-3.7%	-21.3%

Table 10. Asterousia focus sites: AGB Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

The general trend for the whole site after an initial decrease between 2016 and 2018 exhibits a recovery of potential service supply with respect to the reference year, particularly evident in 2019 (-12%) and 2020 (+11%). Again 2022 is characterised by a marked decrease (-16%), but the average loss in service supply is more evident in the wester areas of Pagadaikion (-26.1%) and Miamous (-21.3%) then in the eastern areas. Here a continuous positive trend with respect to the baseline is detected in Paranyfom until 2021, even if the trend start to decrease already in 2020. Nevertheless, even if with the respect to the reference year the relative loss in 2022 is almost negligible (-0.25%), the relative decrease observed in 2022 with respect to 2021 is similar to those observed in the other sites. Figure 28 eventually shows the yearly raster maps for AGB supply in the Asterousia site.

Figure 28. Annual AGB indicator values estimates for Asterousia site. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

In Nestos River delta, the yearly mean supply of the **AGB provisioning service** (Figure 29) shows an overall continuously positive trend between 2015 and 2021 (Table 11), followed by a 15% drop in 2022.

AGB	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.02	1.00	0.85
Mean	0.73	0.70	0.70	0.72	0.71	0.71	0.71	0.59
Min	-0.02	0.01	0.00	-0.01	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.23
Stdev	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.10
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	4.15%	0.00%	0.83%	3.15%	1.73%	1.91%	2.49%	-14.78%
<i>Previous year</i>		-3.98%	0.83%	2.31%	-1.38%	0.17%	0.57%	-16.85%

Table 11. Nestos River delta: AGB Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2016).

Figure 29. Annual AGB indicator values estimates for Nestos River delta. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2016).

The assessment of land degradation processes due to soil salinization in the Nestos River delta resorted to the five RSI presented in A2 deliverable A2.1 "Indicators for the evaluation of restoration actions to combat degradation/desertification", summarised in the following table:

Soil Salinity Indices	SSI₁ Soil Salinity Index-2	$\sqrt{R_{[520:600]} * R_{[630:690]}}$	$\sqrt{Green * Red}$	Douaoui et al. (2006); Khan et al. (2001);- Yahiaoui et al. (2015)
	SSI₂ Soil Salinity Index-2	$2 * R_{[520:600]} - (R_{[630:690]} + R_{[770:900]})$	$2 * Green - (Red + NIR)$	Douaoui and Lepinard (2010); Yahiaoui et al. (2015)
	SSI₃ Soil Salinity Index-1	$\sqrt{R_{[630:690]}^2 + R_{[520:600]}^2}$	$\sqrt{Red^2 + Green^2}$	Douaoui et al. (2006); Yahiaoui et al. (2015)
	SI Soil Salinity	$\frac{R_{[530:590]} * R_{[640:670]}}{R_{[450:510]}}$	$\frac{Green * Red}{Blue}$	Elhag et al. (2016)
	SASI Soil Adjusted Salinity Index	$\frac{R_{[630:690]}}{100 * R_{[450:520]}^2}$	$\frac{Red}{100 * Blue^2}$	Yahiaoui et al. (2015)

Table 12. Soil salinity indices derived from remote sensing (Tarantino et al. 2023).

The problem of **soil salinization** in the Nestos River delta has been well documented in the literature (Gkioungkis et al., 2015; Gkioungkis et al., 2014; Gkioungkis et al., 2011; Gkioungkis et al., 2010; Kallioras et al., 2006; Pliakas et al., 2001). Unfortunately soil salinity data for the area are not available so the analysis for the selection of the sounder and realistic RSI of soil salinity status had to rely on indirect evidence from available information. According to Gkioungkis et al., 2015 it is the eastern side of the delta to be affected by soil salinity: "Almost 10 km² of land in the study area has been deteriorated due to high concentrations of soluble salts and exchangeable sodium. It is evident that approximately 15 km² of the unconfined aquifers are degraded with increasing quantities of soluble salts. Consequently, the soil quality for agricultural purposes is often problematic. The main causes for soil salinization in the study area can be hierarchically summarized as follows: lack of freshwater sources and irrigation with saline groundwater, poor soil drainage, shallow groundwater table with high salt contents, low precipitation and increased water losses during the dry season". Figure 30 shows the area surveyed by Gkioungkis et al. (2015) with the localization of soil samples (0-30 cm) along with their characterization in terms of salinity class as follows: slightly saline (ECe: 2000–4000 μS/cm, pH<8.5) or saline to saline-alkali soil (ECe N 4000 μS/cm, pH<8.5) according to US Salinity Laboratory (Richards, 1954).

If the eastern side of the delta is characterised by the occurrence of salt affected soils, as proved by data from literature, the pattern of the different RSI should confirm that to some extent. We then compared the spatial distribution of the five soli salinity indices listed in Table 12 to assess if and to which extent they would support the occurrence of salt affected soils.

Furthermore, according to the last update of CORINE land cover (EEA, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.2909/71c95a07-e296-44fc-b22b-415f42acdf0>) the area is characterized by the presence of land cover units classified as salt marshes (CLC Code 421) which again could be detected and highlighted by the soil salinity indices from remote sensing.

Figure 30. Nestos River delta: evidence of soil salinization (from Gkiougkis et al., 2015)

Figure 31 shows the spatial distribution of the five RSI of soil salinity along with the occurrence of salt marshes according to CORINE land cover. RSI values refer all to 2015 and have been 0-1 normalised. From the patterns in the maps it can be noted how four out of five indices have substantially the same pattern, but the only one that seems to somehow match the occurrence of salt marshes and the locations of salt affected soil samples in SoSI2.

Figure 31. Nestos River delta: comparison of the spatial patterns of RS soil salinity indices (2015) in the salt affect area of the eastern delta.

A further indirect confirmation the SoSi2 might be the RS soil salinity index that better describes the status of land degradation related to the occurrence of salt affect soils lies in the results of correlation analysis and from the RSIs zonal statistics for the LULC units of CORINE (Figure 32).

Figure 31. Nestos River delta: comparison of the spatial patterns of RS soil salinity indices average values (2015) for the CORINE LULC units.

The spatial patterns of average values of soil salinity indices from RS for the LULC units of CORINE represented in figure 32 have hardly a plausible physical meaning for none of the tested indices with the sole exception of SoSI2, which is the only one to display highest values along the coast and in the salt marshes and the lowest values in the non-irrigated forest areas along the Nestos River.

Furthermore, among the five indices, SoSI2 is the only one to exhibit statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) with a group of environmental covariates which are generally associated with the occurrence of salt affected soils (Table 13). SoSI2 is negatively correlated with elevation ($r = -0.225$) and slope ($r = -0.100$), positively correlated with the Topographic Wetness Index (TWI, $r = 0.147$), and negatively correlated with the distance from the coastline ($r = -0.325$). In all case the correlation is statistically significant.

<i>RSI</i>	SOSI3_2016	SOSI2_2016	SOSI1_2016	SOSA_201	SASI_2016
Terrain, LULC					
DEM	-0.061	-0.225	-0.061	-0.058	0.055
Slope	-0.038	-0.100	-0.038	-0.046	0.041
CatchmentS	-0.075	-0.122	-0.075	-0.082	0.045
ModiCatAre	-0.047	0.045	-0.047	-0.048	-0.012
TWI	0.030	0.147	0.030	0.034	-0.067
River_prox	0.175	0.233	0.175	0.172	-0.060
Coast_prox	-0.001	-0.325	-0.001	0.014	0.056

Table 13. Correlation coefficient of soil salinity indices derived from remote sensing with environmental covariates.

These result clearly and strongly highlight the fact the relying solely on RSIs might lead to misleading conclusion and wrong assessments when they are properly contextualized and supported by ground truth data or any evidence stemming from other sources of information about the environmental covariate and drivers affecting in this case the occurrence of salt affected soils.

Assuming the same reference year of the other indicators (2016), the temporal trend of the degradation process due to salt accumulation in soils, and based on 0-1 normalized values of SoSI2, is summarised in Table 14. A continuous positive trend with respect to the baseline can be observed between 2017 and 2022, with an overall increase of 5.5%. The baseline and final maps of the indicator are shown in figure 32.

SOSI2_Std_2016	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.952	1.000	1.027	1.011	1.001	1.022	0.997	1.029
Mean	0.458	0.450	0.471	0.465	0.471	0.466	0.469	0.483
Min	0.000	0.000	0.000	-0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001
Stdev	0.104	0.111	0.096	0.102	0.093	0.096	0.100	0.097
<i>Baseline 2016</i>	1.71%	0.00%	4.71%	3.30%	4.63%	3.47%	4.18%	7.31%
<i>Previous year</i>		-1.68%	4.71%	-1.35%	1.29%	-1.10%	0.68%	3.00%

Table 14. Nestos River delta: SoS Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2016).

Figure 32. SoSI2 indicator values estimates for Nestos River delta for 2016 and 2022. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2016).

The maps of the relative differences 2022-2016 for the indicators of ES supply and degradation process due to soil salinization are depicted in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Relative differences 2022-2016 for the indicator of ES supply and DP due to salinization in Nestos River delta.

Similarly for the Asterousia site and for the four focus sites within Asterousia, the maps of relative differences 2022-2015 for the indicators of ES supply are depicted in Figures 34 and 35 respectively (for the AGB provisioning service).

Figure 33. Relative differences 2022-2015 for the indicator of ES supply in Asterousia case study area.

Relative change in ES provision - Pegaidakion

Figure 34a. Relative differences 2022-2015 for the indicator of AEG supply in Pegaidakion focus area.

Figure 34b. Relative differences 2022-2015 for the indicator of AEG supply in Asterousia focus areas: Mioamous (top), Paranyfom (centre) and Xondrou (bottom).

5. Italian case study areas: Alta Murgia and Palo Laziale

Alta Murgia is a SAC and Special Protection Area (SPA), code IT9120007, and it includes the Alta Murgia National Park established in 2004, with a total surface of the entire Natura2000 area of ca 1259 km² and an average elevation of 455 m a.s.l. It is characterized by the presence of highly diverse unique ecosystems (Figure 35) and of endemic and threatened grassland species.

Figure 35. Ecosystems of the Alta Murgia National Park (Photos: F. Ungaro)

During the last three decades, the dominant semi-natural grassland ecosystem characterized by extensive land use was exposed to accelerated processes of land degradation, habitat

fragmentation and biotic contamination (e.g., woody encroachment), followed by loss of local biodiversity within and next to its borders, due to both agricultural intensification (transformation of grassland pastures into agricultural cereal crops) and land abandonment. Furthermore, the long-term below-average rainfall, the increase of quarrying activities, the realization of wind farm infrastructures, fire events and the spread of invasive species contribute to the threat to the ecosystem, which is in danger of severe degradation beyond its capacity to recover.

Palo Laziale is a flat coastal area of about 130 hectares. The area, consisting mostly of an oak floodplain forest with some temporary ponds, high Mediterranean shrubs dominated by *Phillyrea angustifolia*, *P. latifolia* and *Pistacia lentiscus* and a meadow extending for about 18 hectares between the forest and the beach forms the core of the 'Bosco di Palo Laziale' Natura 2000 which is now in a state of serious decline. In Palo Laziale climate change has exacerbated forest depletion and unsustainable forestry practices have led to an over competition for resources among trees.

Table 15 summarizes the settings of ES assessment and mapping for the two Italian CSAs.

CSA	Area	ES	Type of ES	CICES v1.5	Proxy	Units	Input res.	Output res.	Baseline	Time interval	EPSG
Alta Murgia	1259 km ²	AGCS	Regulating	2.1.1.2	MOD17 NPP	C Mg/ha	500 m	25 m	2015	2015-2022	3035
		SEC	Regulating	2.2.1.1/2.2.1.3	RUSLE (PSE-ASE)	Mg/ha/y	100 m	25 m	2015	2015-2022	3035
		AGB	Provision	1.1.5.x/1.1.1.x	NDVI Sentinel2	-	20 m	25 m	2015	2015-2022	3035
Palo Laziale	1.29 km ²	AGCS	Regulating	2.1.1.2	MOD17 NPP	C Mg/ha	500 m	10 m	2015	2015-2022	3035
		AGB	Provision	1.1.5.x/1.1.1.x	NDVI Sentinel2	-	20 m	10 m	2015	2015-2022	3035
		DIED	Degradation	n.a.	NDWI Sentinel2	-	20 m	10 m	2015	2015-2022	3035

Table 15. Setting of ES assessment for the Italian CSAs.

In order to estimate and map AGCS in the two sites, MODIS17 NPP (resolution 500 m) were retrieved resorting to GEE fir the period 2015-2022. In the case of Palo Laziale, due to the very small size of the site, it was necessary to enlarge the area to the whole municipality of Ladispoli in order to have enough observations for the statistical analysis. Yearly mean values and their 95% confidence intervals are shown in the box & whisker plot in Figure 36, where the temporal pattern in C stock accumulation is rather distinct in the two areas.

Figure 36. NPP (Mg C ha⁻¹) yearly means for Alt Murgia (left) and Ladispoli (right).

In Alta Murgia NPP is characterised by higher variability than in Palo Laziale, with a maximum in 2016 (6.6 Mg C/ha) and a minimum in 2022 (5.1 Mg C/ha), but mean values for 2017, 2021 and 2022 are all below 5.5 Mg C/ha, while between 2018 and 2020 they are very close to the overall mean of the whole period considered (6.1 Mg C/ha). In Ladispoli though, the trend is quite different, with values above the overall mean of the period (8.3 Mg C/ha) between 2015 and 2020, when the maximum mean value of the whole series is observed (8.9 Mg C/ha). A significant drop characterise the last two years, with a minimum in 2022 (7.3 Mg C/ha).

The MLR equation calibrated to downscale NPP values of the baseline year from the original 500m resolution to the finer target resolutions, have the following form for Alta Murgia (N = 5263, reference year 2015, resolution 25 m):

$$NPP_{2015} = 10.615 + (4.123 * NDVI_{2015}) + (-0.004 * DEM_{3m}) + (-0.0008 * blue_{2015}) + (0.00006 * SOSI1_{2015}) + (-0.0044 * green_{2015}) + (-0.801 * NDBSI_{2015}) + (-0.0003 * IR_{2015})$$

while in the case of Ladispoli (N = 5265, reference year 2015, resolution 10m) it has the following form:

$$NPP_{2015} = 12.59 + (0.0000039 * catcharea) + (1.0779 * catchslope) + (0.0038 * dem) + (0.000011 * modcatcharea) + (-0.13238 * twi) + (-0.0042 * blue_{2015}) + (0.0042 * IR_{2015}) + (0.00065 * IRn_{2015}) + (-0.00166 * SOSA_{2015}) + (-0.000064 * SOSI1_{2015}) + (-0.00023 * SOSI2_{2015})$$

Figure 37. Observed vs estimated NPP (Mg C/ha) for Alta Murgia (left) and Ladispoli (right).

Figure 38. Observed vs estimated NPP (Mg C/ha) for Alta Murgia (left) and Ladispoli (right).

Figure 8 shows for the baseline reference year (2015) the scatterplots between observed and estimated NPP values for the two Italian ND4DL sites. As in the other CSAs, NPP values were estimated for all the years up to 2022, and then 0-1 normalised to estimate the annual potential supply of the AGCS regulation service for the two CSAs, as shown in Figure 39 and Figure 40, for Alta Murgia and Palo laziale respectively.

Figure 39. Annual AGCS indicator values estimates for Alta Murgia site. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

Figure 40. Annual AGCS indicator values estimates for Palo Laziale. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

The relative changes in the potential supply of AGCS regulating service with respect to the baseline year and to the previous year within the period 2015-2016 are summarized in Table 16 and in Tabel 17, for Alta Murgia and Palo Laziale respectively.

AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Mean	0.536	0.613	0.593	0.633	0.631	0.641	0.601	0.286
Min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Stdev	0.12	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.06
Baseline 2015	0.00%	14.28%	10.60%	18.00%	17.60%	19.55%	12.03%	-46.73%
Previous year		14.28%	-3.22%	6.68%	-0.34%	1.66%	-6.29%	-52.46%

Table 16. Alta Murgia site: AGCS Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015) .

AGCS	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.843	0.810	0.974	0.733	0.592
Mean	0.472	0.699	0.601	0.585	0.517	0.648	0.465	0.261
Min	0.000	0.205	0.098	0.211	0.072	0.154	0.051	0.000
Stdev	0.118	0.117	0.091	0.078	0.079	0.078	0.070	0.096
Baseline 2015	0.00%	47.92%	27.20%	23.85%	9.50%	37.14%	-1.49%	-44.83%
Previous year		47.92%	-14.00%	-2.64%	-11.59%	25.24%	-28.17%	-44.00%

Table 17. Palo Laziale site: AGCS Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015) .

The soil erosion control (by vegetation) regulating service was assessed and mapped only in the Alta Murgia site, resorting to the same methodological approach implemented for the Spanish and Greek CSAs. The MLR calibrated for the baseline year (2015) to downscale the estimated soil mass retained by vegetation from 100 to 25 m resolution (Figure 41) has the following form (N = 4267):

$$\text{Soil mass retained by Vegetation}_{2015} = 1.719 + (0.285 * \text{Slope}) + (0.0000115 * \text{ModCatchArea}) + (-0.166 * \text{TWI}) + (-1.684 * \text{CatchmentSlope}) + (-0.000332 * \text{DEM3}) + (-0.000266 * \text{Aspect}) + (-0.0000106 * \text{CatchArea}) + (0.000161 * \text{SOSA}_{2015}) + (-0.001518 * \text{green}_{2015}) + (0.000298 * \text{SWIR}_{2015}) + (-3.009 * \text{NDSI}_{2015}) + (3.301 * \text{NDVI}_{2015}) + (-0.000266 * \text{IR}_{2015}) + (0.00135 * \text{blue}_{2015}) + (2.430 * \text{BI}_{2015}) + (0.382 * \text{NDBSI}_{2015})$$

Figure 41. Observed and MLR estimated soil mass retained by vegetation (log scale) for Alta Murgia (baseline year 2015).

The spatial distribution of the annual values for the SEC regulating service at 25m spatial resolution in Alta Murgia is shown in Figure 42. The raster statistics computed for each annual map are summarised in Table 18.

Figure 42. Annual SEC indicator values estimates for Alta Murgia site. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

SEC	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.04	1.20	1.06
Mean	0.203	0.211	0.193	0.220	0.219	0.218	0.193	0.171
Min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Stdev	0.35	0.48	0.44	0.53	0.51	0.53	0.45	0.42
Baseline 2015	0.00%	3.79%	-4.97%	8.42%	7.86%	7.23%	-5.16%	-15.60%
Previous year		3.79%	-8.44%	14.09%	-0.52%	-0.58%	-11.56%	-11.00%

Table 18. Alta Murgia site: SEC Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015) .

As in the other NL4DL CSAs, in both the Italian sites the AGB provisioning service was estimated adopting the baseline NDVI as proxy and resorting to a 0-1 interval standardization it made possible to compare the indicators and their relative changes with respect to the selected baseline. Results for the two Italian CSAs summarised in Table 19 and in Table 20, for Alta

Murgia and Palo Laziale respectively, while Figure 43 shows the multiple histograms for NDVI values in 2015, 2020 (maximum mean NDVI value in both sites) and in 2022 (minum mean NDVI value in both sites). It can be clearly seen in the figure that while in Alta Murgia the mean value for 2015 is very close to the low value observed in 2022, in Palo Laziale the 2015 mean value is very close to the high mean value observed in 2020. These differences in the distributions of the data underlying the AGB indicator statistics, and their relative differences with respect to the same baseline year, explain the differences in the figures reported in the tables below.

Figure 43. Multiple histograms for NDVI values in 2015, 2020 and 2022 for the two Italian CSAs, Alta Murgia (left) and Palo laziale (right).

AGB	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.00	1.00	0.99	0.97	0.99	0.97	0.97	0.75
Mean	0.389	0.503	0.463	0.547	0.530	0.550	0.481	0.426
Min	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.12
Stdev	0.35	0.48	0.44	0.53	0.51	0.53	0.45	0.42
Baseline 2016	0.00%	29.18%	19.08%	40.50%	36.08%	41.25%	23.63%	9.48%
Previous year		29.18%	-7.82%	17.99%	-3.15%	3.80%	-12.47%	-11.45%

Table 19. Alta Murgia site: AGB Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

AGB	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.774	0.741	0.720	0.738	0.735	0.750	0.748	0.491
Mean	0.661	0.657	0.654	0.683	0.696	0.708	0.659	0.310
Min	0.139	0.132	0.125	0.144	0.154	0.155	0.109	0.056
Stdev	0.131	0.134	0.088	0.106	0.085	0.081	0.119	0.060
Baseline 2015	0.00%	-0.61%	-1.06%	3.33%	5.30%	7.11%	-0.30%	-53.10%
Previous year		-0.61%	-0.46%	4.43%	1.90%	1.72%	-6.92%	-52.96%

Table 20. Palo Laziale site: AGB Indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

The map of potential supply of AGB provisioning service are given in Figure 44 and Figure 45 for Alta Murgia and Palo Laziale respectively.

Figure 42. Annual AGB indicator values estimates for Alta Murgia site. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

Figure 43. Annual AGB indicator values estimates for Palo Laziale. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

Given the current trend affecting the status of the vegetation in Palo Laziale, a third indicator was derived to assess and map the drought induced ecosystem degradation risk (DIEDr). To this goal an indicator was chosen and tested from the RSIs list provided by A2, i.e. NDWI.

The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI, Gao, 1996) is known to be strongly related to the plant water content and it is therefore a very good proxy for plant water stress. NDWI is dimensionless and varies between -1 to +1, depending on the leaf water content but also on the vegetation type and cover. High values of NDWI correspond to high vegetation water content and to high vegetation fraction cover. Low NDWI values correspond to low vegetation water content and low vegetation fraction cover. In period of water stress, NDWI will decrease, as shown in Table 21 for Palo Laziale (Figure 44).

NDWI	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	0.585	0.493	0.490	0.478	0.515	0.521	0.524	0.315
Mean	0.264	0.236	0.236	0.265	0.283	0.285	0.248	0.162
Min	-0.206	-0.142	-0.060	-0.078	-0.017	-0.026	-0.116	-0.064
Stdev	0.169	0.147	0.097	0.123	0.104	0.095	0.138	0.080
Baseline 2015	0.00%	-10.50%	-10.54%	0.35%	7.22%	7.87%	-6.00%	-38.53%
Previous year		-10.50%	-0.04%	12.17%	6.84%	0.61%	-12.86%	-34.61%

Table 21. Palo Laziale site: NDWI yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

Figure 43. Annual NDWI for Palo Laziale between 2015 and 2022 ($NDWI = (NIR - SWIR)/(NIR + SWIR)$).

NDWI values were 0-1 normalised taking 2015 as baseline year the definition of the indicator of Drought Induced Ecosystem Degradation risk (DIED), returning the annual statistics reported in Table 22 and the maps depicted in Figure 44. In this case the calculation assumed 1 to be associate with the highest risk, and 0 with the lowest.

DIEDrisk_WI	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Max	1.00	0.92	0.82	0.84	0.76	0.77	0.89	0.82
Mean	0.406	0.441	0.441	0.405	0.382	0.380	0.426	0.535
Min	0.00	0.12	0.12	0.14	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.34
Stdev	0.21	0.19	0.12	0.16	0.13	0.12	0.17	0.10
Baseline 2015	0.00%	8.63%	8.66%	-0.29%	-5.93%	-6.47%	4.93%	31.66%
Previous year		8.63%	0.03%	-8.24%	-5.65%	-0.57%	12.19%	25.47%

Table 21. Palo Laziale site: DIEDr indicator yearly raster statistics and their relative changes in mean value with respect to the baseline (2015).

Figure 44. Annual DIEDr indicator Palo Laziale between 2015 and 2022. Values are standardised with respect to the baseline year (2015).

Figure 45 summarizes the relative changes (with reference to the baseline and to the previous year) in the three indicators selected for Palo Laziale and show the maps of the relative change occurred between 2022 and 2015.

Figure 45. Relative differences 2022-2015 for the indicator of ES supply and DP in Palo Laziale case study area.

The AGCS indicator for the years 2015 to 2022 in Palo Laziale is characterized by a constantly positive trend with respect to the baseline, with the highest increase in 2016 (+48% ca.) and 2020 (+37% ca.). The years 2021 and 2022 are characterised by a severe decrease of the mean indicator values, with a drop with respect to the previous year of -28 and -44% respectively for 2021 and 2022. The trend of the AGB indicator is characterized by a negative variation with respect to the baseline for 2016 and 2017, followed by three years of constant increase between 2018-2020, with the steepest increase with respect to the previous year in 2018 (+4.43%). The trend becomes again negative in the last two years, with a decrease with respect to the previous year of almost -7% in 2021 and of -53% in 2022. A very similar trend but with the opposite sign, is observed for the indicator of Drought Induced Ecosystem Degradation risk (DIED) based on the NDWI: the yearly changes are of the same order of magnitude observed for the AGB indicator.

Figure 46 summarizes the relative changes (with reference to the baseline and to the previous year) in the three indicators selected for Alta Murgia and show the maps of the relative change occurred between 2022 and 2015.

Figure 46. Relative differences 2022-2015 for the indicator of ES supply in Alta Murgia case study area.

In the Alta Murgia site the trend AGB indicator is characterised by a constantly positive sign with respect to the baseline year (2015) with the highest increase in 2018 (+40.5%), as observed in Palo Laziale, and 2020 (+41.3%), while the lowest increase is detected in 2022 (+9.5%). Nevertheless, considering the variations with respect to the previous year along the time series, 2021 and 2022 are characterised by negative changes, equal respectively to -12.5 and -11.5%. Negative changes with respect to the previous year are detected also in 2017 (-7.8%) and 2019 (-3.2%). The AGCS indicator for the years 2015 to 2022 show a constantly positive trend with respect to the baseline, with the highest increase in 2018 (+18% ca.) and 2020 (+20% ca.). Similarly to what observed in Palo laziale, the last two years of the considered time series are characterised by a decrease of the mean indicator values, with a moderate -6.3% drop with respect to the previous year in 2021, and a very severe -52.5% average drop in 2022 affecting the whole area. The changes with respect to the baseline follow a similar trend also for the SEC indicator, characterised in Alta Murgia by negative changes in 2021 (-11.6%) and 2022 (-15.6%), and a positive trend between 2018 and 2020. Again, as for the other indicators, the most notable gain along the time series occurs in 2018 (+8.4%).

6. Conclusions

RS data integrated with thematic data have provided an effective mean to detect and map trends in ES supply and DP intensity in the CSAs. The use of 0-1 normalized indicators allows to compare the observed trends among the different sites, as shown in the radar charts presented in Figures 47 to 50.

Figure 47. AGCS potential supply: comparison of mean annual supply (left) and differences with respect to the previous year (right) in the six NL4DL CSAs.

Figure 48. AGB potential supply: comparison of mean annual supply (left) and differences with respect to the previous year (right) in the six NL4DL CSAs.

Figure 49. SEC potential supply: comparison of mean annual supply (left) and differences with respect to the previous year (right) in four NL4DL CSAs.

Figure 50. Degradation process indicators: comparison of mean annual values and differences with respect to the previous year (right) in two NL4DL CSAs.

From the trends shown in the above Figures, it can be noted that despite the existence of local variations triggered by localized events such as wildfires or climatic events, there are recurring patterns that are evident in all CSAs and in the different indicators. For example, all sites with no exception are affected by a significant drop in the indicators' values in 2022, particularly evident for the AGB and AGCS indicators, and more pronounced in the Italian and Catalan case study sites. On the other side, positive gain in AGB, AGCS and SEC indicators are detected in 2016 and 2018 in all sites where these indicators were assessed, and again the increase is more relevant in the Italian and the Catalan sites. This can be more evident in the stacked columns

charts in Figures 51 to 53, which display the overall trends and how the different CSAs contribute to the overall changes observed in ES potential supply over time.

Figure 51. AGCS potential supply: contribution of the different CSAs to the overall trend observed between 2015 and 2022.

Figure 52. AGB potential supply: contribution of the different CSAs to the overall trend observed between 2015 and 2022.

Figure 52. SEC potential supply: contribution of the different CSAs to the overall trend observed between 2015 and 2022.

Between 2015 and 2022, the overall trends in potential ecosystem supply as modelled via normalized indicators in all CSAs is decreasing, with overall positive gain for all indicators in 2016 and 2018, and to a lesser extent in 2020, and with negative sign in 2019, but not generalized in all sites for the AGB indicator, and significant losses in 2021 which becomes extreme in 2022, particularly for AGCS and AGB.

Results showed that models based on Sentinel-2 indices, combined with terrain attributes and other information, can estimate potential ecosystem services supply in the study areas even when the levels of field-based ecosystem services supplies are low. The RSI-based models can assess ecosystem services more accurately when their indicators mainly depend on green vegetation, such as for erosion prevention and provision of biomass. The use of Sentinel-2 vegetation indices and terrain data to quantify ecosystem services is a first step towards improving the monitoring and assessment of restoration interventions via NbS.

In conclusion the following general remarks can be made:

- The approach for ES/DP assessment and mapping presented in this report and based on the integration of RSI (time dependent) and other environmental drivers (time invariant), proved to be sensitive enough to detect negative changes in ES supply stemming from land degradation processes due to different drivers acting at different scales, such as wildfires and drought, but also positive changes due to ecosystem recovery.
- The results presented here focused on detecting, describing, and mapping yearly changes, but the approach can be easily tailored to finer temporal scales, provided that an adequate number of usable RS imagery supports the selected time interval.

- The methodological workflow is cost-effective as it relies entirely on available free-of-charge web resources and freeware. It can be rapidly implemented in almost any area, providing spatially explicit multi-temporal outputs at a spatial resolution which is sufficient for most ES and DP assessment applications.
- Resorting to 0-1 normalised indicators of potential ES supply or DP intensity allowed to compare responses over time and among sites. Furthermore, it highlights the possibility to switch the focus from the magnitude of biophysically assessed quantities (along with their uncertainties) to trends and relative changes with respect to baseline(s).
- The approach could successfully integrate ground data with indicators from RS into the definition of ES/DP indicators. Such data were regrettably unavailable for the NL4DL CSAs, which somewhat hampered the robustness of the selected indicators even if similar approaches are widely reported in the literature.
- Ground truthing in some of the NL4DL CSAs (Asterousia, El Bruc) has anyway provided insights into the magnitude and extent of the current degradation processes affecting ES supply, proving the adequacy of the proposed methodology.
- In the lack of ground data, relying solely on RSI may result to misleading conclusions and interpretation if they are not integrated, compared, and supported by information derived from other sources which allow to contextualize the evidence stemming from RSIs and to check the plausibility of results.

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